

Formation of thiocyanato bridged dinuclear ruthenium(III) complex ion by the reaction between thiocyanatopentaammineruthenium(III) and aquapentaammine-ruthenium(III) complex ions in aqueous medium

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Mechanistic study on the dinuclear complex formation by the reaction of complex species $[\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{H}_2\text{O}]^{3+}$ and $[\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{SCN}]^{2+}$ was investigated in aqueous medium between 32° and 58°. In aqueous solution, the aqua species exists in equilibrium with the hydroxo species, and both the forms are reactive with the thiocyanato complex. The rate constants at different temperatures have been determined for both the species. The hydroxo form is more reactive than the aqua form. Activation parameters have been evaluated for both the species. An 'I' mechanism seems more probable and 'ion-aggregation' plays an important role in this case as both the species carries similar charge.

Dinuclear ruthenium(III) complexes can be obtained by the 'anation type' of reactions between two complex species, one having an aqua ligand which may be replaced by the other coordinating species. Substitution of aqua ligand in an aqua complex by a number of anions/neutral molecules leads to the synthesis of a number of desired ruthenium(II, III) complexes¹. However, 'ion-clustering' plays an important role in the formation of such complex species and cluster formations are particularly important when the anion-to-cation ratio is high². In the present investigation, we have taken up two complex species with the same type of charges on them – one of the complex species having an 'aqua' ligand on it and the other one having an ambidentate ligand 'thiocyanate' to join two metal centres by bridge formation. Our object is to study the mechanism of dinuclear complex formation by the reaction between two similarly charged complex ions in aqueous medium.

Results and discussion

In the experimental pH range, the aqua complex undergoes hydrolysis and forms an equilibrium mixture with the hydroxo species. pK values of the aqua complex at different temperatures were determined by pH-metric titration of the species with standard sodium hydroxide solution. The pK values are obtained from the half-neutralization point of the titre value. The equilibrium constant (K) values at different temperatures are as follows : at 32°, 3.97 ± 0.03 ; 40°, 3.90 ± 0.05 ; 45°, 3.81 ± 0.04 ; 50°, 3.74 ± 0.03 ; 58°, 3.59 ± 0.05 . The pseudo-first order rate constant (k_{obs}) values as

determined between 32° and 58° and in the pH range 3.12–6.53 are given in Table 1. Below pH ~3.0, acid catalyzed aquation of the thiocyanato complex takes place, so measurements below pH ~3.0 was left out for the present. Rate constant values remain unaltered with varying amounts of each complex provided pseudo-first order conditions are maintained (that is one component is ten times or more than the other one). A plot of k_{obs} vs pH tend towards a limiting value at higher pH and has a full S-shaped profile.

The reactions that take place in the experimental pH range may be given as follows :

In reactions (2) and (3), both the reacting species have like charges, so possibility of ion-pair formation is ruled out.

The rate expression for the reactions may be given as (N_5 stands for $(\text{NH}_3)_5$) :

$$-d/dt([\text{Ru}N_5(\text{H}_2\text{O})] + [\text{Ru}N_5(\text{OH})]) = k_{\text{obs}}([\text{Ru}N_5(\text{H}_2\text{O})] + [\text{Ru}N_5(\text{OH})][\text{Ru}N_5\text{SCN}]) \quad (4)$$

also

$$-d/dt ([RuN_5(H_2O)] + [RuN_5(OH)]) = k_1([RuN_5(H_2O)][RuN_5SCN] + k_2[RuN_5(OH)][RuN_5SCN]) \quad (5)$$

Combining (4) and (5), we have

$$k_{obs} = \frac{k_1[RuN_5H_2O] + k_2[RuN_5OH]}{([RuN_5H_2O] + [RuN_5OH])} = \frac{k_1 [H^+] + k_2 K}{[H^+] + K}, \text{ because } K = \frac{[RuN_5OH] [H^+]}{[RuN_5H_2O]} \quad (6)$$

Eqn. (6) can be arranged in the linear form as

$$\frac{1}{(k_{obs} - k_2)} = \frac{1}{k_1 - k_2} + \frac{K}{[H^+] (k_1 - k_2)} \quad (7)$$

A plot of $\frac{1}{(k_{obs} - k_2)}$ vs $1/[H^+]$ is linear having an intercept of $1/(k_1 - k_2)$.

At high pH value (~6.0 and above), as the concentration of aqua species is negligible, k_{obs} values are solely due to the hydroxo species and at this point k_2 , the rate constant for the reaction of the hydroxo species is the same as k_{obs} . The rate constant for the aqua species (k_1) is obtained from k_2 values and the intercept of the plot. The values of k_1 and k_2 thus determined are given in Table 2, along with the activation parameter values as obtained from Eyrings plot. The dissociation constant values of the aqua complex is also obtained from the slope of the plot. The values thus obtained match excellently with the experimentally determined values (within the limits of experimental error).

Now let us look to the plausible mechanism of the bridge formation reaction. For an I_d mechanism, the reaction given by eqn. (2) may be spitted further as follows :

However, for such a mechanism rate constant should depend on the concentration of the thiocyanatopentaammine complex. No such rate dependency of the thiocyanato complex concentration was observed. Water exchange in $[Ru(H_2O)_5(OH)]^{2+}$ proceeds by an 'I' mechanism rather than 'I_a' mechanism⁴. For the present system also substitution of H_2O by the thiocyanato complex probably takes place by 'I' mechanism.

A 'dissociative' mechanism seems unlikely for the present one. On the other hand, some sort of 'ion-aggregation' takes place between the reacting species where the SCN^- end of the thiocyanato complex plays the leading role. Ruthenium(III) ion is moderately 'soft'. In the 'aqua' complex, H_2O being a hard base ligand, can easily be replaced by the 'soft' sulfur end of the thiocyanato ligand present in the thiocyanato complex, which acts as the 'bridging' group. The role of the ambidentate SCN^- in 'ion-aggregation' and in the formation of the multinuclear ruthenium(III) complex has already been demonstrated⁵. 'Ion-association' between the two reacting species assisted by the bridging ligand SCN^- leads to the formation of the dinuclear complex in the present case. Rate constants for the hydroxo species at all the experimental temperatures are higher than the corresponding rate constant values of the aqua species. At the same time, enthalpy of the reaction of the hydroxo species is also higher,

Table 1. Observed rate constants ($\times 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1}$) at different pH values and temperature* $[Ru(NH_3)_5SCN]^{2+} = 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Ru(NH_3)_5H_2O]^{3+} = 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

32°		40°		45°		50°		58°	
pH	k_{obs}								
3.51	6.30	3.75	10.85	3.12	11.36	3.79	18.18	3.40	22.51
3.90	7.32	4.02	11.89	3.25	11.70	4.07	20.17	3.65	24.76
4.10	7.77	4.16	12.33	3.51	12.56	4.21	20.92	4.16	28.69
5.30	9.13	4.59	12.71	3.79	13.69	4.82	21.47	4.76	30.70
6.15	9.33	5.08	13.95	4.11	14.95	5.21	23.01	6.15	31.71
6.37	9.50	6.01	13.98	4.25	15.48	6.13	23.01	6.20	31.69
6.39	9.52	6.21	14.13	4.75	16.79	6.31	23.06	6.46	31.89
		6.31	14.19	5.38	17.25	6.53	23.29		
				6.47	17.39				

*Deviation, $\pm 3\%$.

Table 2. Rate constants k_1 and k_2 and activation parameters of the aqua and hydroxo complexes*

Temp. °C	$10^5 k_1$ s ⁻¹	$10^5 k_2$ s ⁻¹
32	5.25	9.50
40	8.42	14.20
45	10.25	17.40
50	12.78	23.30
58	16.52	31.90
ΔH^\ddagger , kJ mol ⁻¹	31.8 ± 2	37.6 ± 6
ΔS^\ddagger , J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	-225 ± 10	-200 ± 10

*Deviation, ±3%.

showing a stronger Ru–OH bond. This is in full agreement with H₂O exchange reactions in monohydroxyruthenium(III) species, where $\Delta H^\ddagger = 136.9 \pm 6$ kJ mol⁻¹, $\Delta S^\ddagger = 100.5 \pm 18$ kJ mol⁻¹ for the exchange of a water molecule⁴.

Experimental

Preparation of complexes : Pentaamminethiocyanato-ruthenium(III) perchlorate and aquapentaammineruthenium(III) perchlorate were prepared according to literature procedures³. Purity of the samples was checked by elemental analysis and spectral matching of authentic samples as given in the literature.

All other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Double-distilled water was used for all solutions.

Kinetics of the reactions : Reaction mixtures for kinetic runs were prepared from appropriate quantities for the complexes [Ru(NH₃)₅SCN](ClO₄)₂ and [Ru(NH₃)₅(H₂O)](ClO₄)₃ in the desired ratio to have a pseudo-first order rate plot. A set of experiments were carried out with thiocyanato and aqua complex concentrations as 1×10^{-4} and 1×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, respectively. Other sets of experiments were also carried out with concentrations of the two complexes as 1×10^{-4} and 2×10^{-3} ; 1×10^{-3} and 1×10^{-4} ; 2×10^{-3} and 1×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³, respectively. Ionic strengths were maintained at 11×10^{-4} and 21×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ without the assistance of any other indifferent electrolyte. Ionic strength was calculated individually in each case as

$$I = 1/2 \sum C_i Z_i^2$$

where, I is the total ionic strength, C_i the concentration of the i -th ion, Z_i the valence of the i -th ion.

pH was maintained with self-buffered system of aqua-hydroxo complex equilibrium. The kinetics were followed

spectrophotometrically at 510 nm corresponding to one of the absorption maxima of the mixture of complexes in the thermostated optical chamber ($\pm 0.1^\circ$) of a Hitachi 200-20 spectrophotometer. pH was measured with a Systronics pH meter. All reactions follow a pseudo-first order rate equation. Rate constant values were determined by Guggenheims plot. Activation parameters were evaluated by the plot of $\log kh/KT$ vs $1/T$, where k , h , K and T stands for rate constant, Planck's constant, Boltzmann's constant and absolute temperature.

Identification of product complex : Aqueous solution of the experimental complexes (concentration of each complex, 1×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³) were mixed and placed in a thermostat for 2 days at 50°. Upon completion of the reaction, the mixture containing the product complex and other species were quenched by cooling in ice-water ($\sim 5-10$) and then eluted from a cation exchange resin column (15 cm long, Bio-rad AG 50 W \times 2) with aqueous sodium nitrate solution. Sodium nitrate concentration in the eluent was gradually increased from an initial 0.3 mol dm⁻³ to a final 3.0 mol dm⁻³. Aliquots (10 cm³) of solutions were collected and their UV-visible spectra were recorded. The dinuclear species eluted at the approximate sodium ion concentration 2.5 and 2.8 mol dm⁻³ and was clearly separated on the column from other reaction components. This fraction was concentrated on a rotary evaporator and on treatment with a solution of sodium perchlorate, the less soluble perchlorate salt of the thiocyanato bridged dinuclear complex [Ru(NH₃)₅–SCN–Ru(NH₃)₃](ClO₄)₅ crystallized out. It was recrystallized from aqueous solution and subjected to analysis (Found : Ru, 22.00; N, 16.42; C, 1.43; H, 3.40; Cl, 19.27. Calcd. for : Ru, 21.78; N, 16.60; C, 1.29; H, 3.23; Cl, 19.14%), λ_{max} 208 (ϵ 4.32), 302 (2.89), 504 nm (0.62).

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